

Hemophagocytic Subtype of Intravascular Large B-cell Lymphoma: An Unusual Finding

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ABSTRACT

Intravascular lymphoma (IVL) is an aggressive and rare disease with a poor prognosis classified by the World Health Organization (WHO) as a subtype of diffuse large B-cell lymphoma (DLBCL). It is characterized by a proliferation of large neoplastic B cells within the lumina of small blood vessels, with minimal or no infiltration of the surrounding extravascular tissue. The hemophagocytic subtype typically occurs in adults, with a median age of around 70 years and with no sex predilection. Herein, we present a case with hemophagocytic syndrome, including splenomegaly, fever, cytopenia (anemia and thrombocytopenia), macrophage activation syndrome and lymphocytosis observed on peripheral blood smear, which developed for seven weeks in a 75-year-old lady. Histological study and immunohistochemical staining of the bone marrow biopsy revealed a proliferation of atypical lymphomatous cells within the lumen of small blood vessels.

CLINICAL CASE

We describe a case of 75 years old women with no significant medical history, in whom the diagnosis was established through histopathological analysis of a bone marrow biopsy (BOM). She was referred to the hematology department for the management of a general health deterioration, splenomegaly, bicytopenia (anemia and thrombocytopenia), macrophage activation syndrome, and lymphocytosis observed on peripheral blood smear. Histological study of the bone marrow biopsy showed a proliferation of large atypical lymphomatous cells within the lumen of blood vessels (Figure 1A). On immunohistochemistry, these cells expressed CD20 and MUM1 (Figure 1B). Additionally, endothelial cells lining the sinusoidal capillaries containing the tumor cells showed positive staining with CD34. (Figure 1C)

Figure 1: (A) Bone marrow biopsy in Hematoxylin and Eosin staining (H&Ex40) showing a proliferation of atypical lymphomatous cells within the lumen of blood vessels. (B) Positive immunostaining of intravascular tumor cells with CD20; (C) Positive immunostaining of vascular walls with CD34.